

Synthesis and biological evaluation of some substituted 1,2,4-triazoles

R. H. Udupi^{*a}, Ashok Kushnoor^a and A. R. Bhat^b

^aDepartment of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, V. L. College of Pharmacy, Raichur-584 101, India

^bCollege of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Manipal-576 119, India

Manuscript received 12 June 1998, revised 3 May 1999, accepted 3 June 1999

4-(4-Pyridoyl)-3-substituted-5-phenylazo-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazolidines and 1,2,4-triazolo Mannich bases have been synthesised and screened for biological activities.

Various 1,2,4-triazoles and *N*-bridged heterocycles derived from them are found to possess diverse pharmacological activities¹. The synthesis and reactions of 4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles have been reviewed². The 1,2,4-triazole nucleus has been incorporated into a wide variety of therapeutically interesting drugs³. Prompted by these observations and in continuation of our work on the synthesis of biologically active nitrogen and sulphur containing heterocycles, we report here the synthesis of triazolothiadiazolidines and triazolo Mannich bases incorporating a well known antitubercular drug, isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH) moiety with a view to enhance the activity of the triazole derivatives.

4-(*N*-Pyridylcarboxamido)-5-mercapto-3-substituted-1,2,4-triazoles (2) required as starting compounds were obtained in one-pot reaction by heating INH with potassium dithiocarbazinate⁴ (1) (Scheme 1). 4-(4-Pyridoyl)-3-substituted-5-phenylazo-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazolidines (3) were prepared in a single-pot reaction by heating 2 with a phenylisothiocyanate in DMF. Triazolo Mannich bases (4) were obtained by reacting 2a with various compounds of biological interest under Mannich conditions.

Results and Discussion

Biological activities : Compounds 3 and 4 were screened for *in vitro* antibacterial and antifungal activities against *S. aureus*, *B. pumillis*, *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa* and *A. niger* by cup-plate method⁵ using concentration 50 µg ml⁻¹ in DMSO. Antitubercular activity of compounds 3a, 3e, 3g, 3j, 4a, 4e, 4g and 4j was studied at concentrations 100, 10 and 1 µg ml⁻¹ by observing the growth pattern of the human strain H₃₇R_v of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in LJ medium in the presence of test compounds⁶. The solvent used was DMSO.

Compounds 3a, 3d, 3g and 4g (14–15 mm) showed moderate activity with ampicillin against *S. aureus* (18 mm), 4a, 4b, 4e and 4g (17–18 mm) showed more potent activity than ampicillin against *B. pumillis* (14 mm), 4a, 4g, 4i (18 mm) revealed comparable activity with ampicillin.

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) INH, 180^o, (ii) PhNCS, DMF, (iii) Mannich treaction.

lin against *E. coli* (18 mm) while **4d**, **4g** and **4j** (20 mm) had comparable activity with ampicillin against *P. aeruginosa* (20 mm). All compounds showed moderate activity with benzylpenicillin against the same organisms. Compounds **3d**, **4i**, **4l** and **4j** (19–21 mm) showed comparable activity with griseofulvin (19 mm) against *A. niger*. The compounds screened for antitubercular activity were found to inhibit the human strain H₃₇R_v of *M. tuberculosis* at 100 µg ml⁻¹ concentration, while the standard streptomycin showed inhibitory activity at 10 µg ml⁻¹ concentration. Anti-inflammatory activity of compounds **3c**, **3g**, **4a**, **4g** and **4h** were assessed at 100 mg/kg oral dose by acute carrageenan induced oedema in rat paw following the reported technique⁷ using ibuprofen as reference. The compounds did not show significant activity.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined on a Toshniwal apparatus in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 599B spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a EM 390 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. Purity of compounds was checked by tlc using silica gel G. All the compounds showed satisfactory elemental analyses.

4-(4-Pyridoyl)-3-substituted-5-phenylazo-1,2,4-triazolo-[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazolidines (3a): A mixture of a solution of **2a** (0.01 mol) in DMF and phenylisothiocyanate (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 28–30 h and then cooled. It was poured in cold water and the resulting solid was washed with water, dried and crystallized from aqueous ethanol: **3a** (70%), m.p. 292–94; ν_{\max} 1700 (C=O of N–C=O), 1640 (C=N), 1610 (C=C), 1480 (C–N), 690 cm⁻¹ (C–S), absence of band for SH; δ 8.1–7.3 (10H, m, ArH), 8.7 (4H, m, pyridyl); *m/z* 398, 332, 308, 143 and 77. Similarly other compounds (**3b–j**; yields 60–75%) were prepared and crystallized from aqueous ethanol: **3b**, m.p., 282°; **c**, 265°; **d**, 248°; **e**, 275°; **f**, 132°; **g**, 85°; **h**, 95°; **i**, 68°; **j**, 62°.

Mannich bases from 4-(N-pyridylcarboxamido)-5-mercapto-3-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole (4g): A mixture of **2a** (0.1 mol), 4-nitroanthranilic acid (0.1 mol) and formaldehyde

(0.2 mol) in glacial acetic acid (4 ml) was refluxed for 4 h and then cooled. It was kept overnight and poured in cold saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallized from dilute acetic acid: **4g** (75%), m.p. 114°; ν_{\max} 3300 (NH), 3000 (OH of COOH), 1692 (C=O of COOH), 1653 (C=O of CONH), 1636 (C=N), 1616 (C=C), 1473 (C–N), 1343 (NO₂), 1020 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ 3.57 (2H, s, CH₂), 5.3 (1H, s, NH), 5.7 (1H, s, NHCO), 8.3–7.2 (8H, m, ArH), 9.1 (4H, m, pyridyl) and 12.1 (1H, s, OH of COOH); *m/z* 491 (M⁺ 100%), 296, 212, 177. Similarly, other compounds (**4a–f**, **h–j**; yields 55–78%) were prepared and crystallized from dilute acetic acid: **4a**, m.p. 190°; **b**, 173°; **c**, 210°; **d**, 185°; **e**, 276°; **f**, 184°; **h**, 255°; **i**, 140°; **j**, 153°.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Dr. P. G. Shivanand and Mr. Kotian, Department of Microbiology, KMC Manipal, for the help rendered in carrying out antitubercular screening.

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